

**"Maintaining Order:
Law, Morality, and Justice in
Sherlock Holmes"**

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Mémoire de Master Etudes Anglophones
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2024-2025

Cover Image: Sidney Paget, *Portrait of Sherlock Holmes*, 1904.
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ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

First of all, I would like to warmly thank my thesis supervisor Mrs. Béatrice Laurent for her support, precious advice and much appreciated insight on my work. This thesis would not have existed if not for her; as well as my professors from the Université Bordeaux Montaigne, who throughout the past two years have shared precious knowledge in their courses. I would also like to thank Mr. Flavien Bardet for his participation in my jury.

I would additionally like to acknowledge Mrs Coralline Dupuy, professor at the University of Galway, who showed me that writing about Sherlock Holmes was possible and who warmly encouraged me to go down that path.

On a more personal note, I want to firstly thank Zhang Hao, who has always shown me that anything is possible if you decide to follow your dreams. You are my role model when it comes to passion, discipline and success. I would like to thank ZB1 and &TEAM whose songs were the soundtrack of my life for the past two years. Good music really does get you through tough moments.

To all my friends, thank you. You bring me the most precious motivation of all: joy. To Cait who provided me access to many articles through her university's subscriptions, to Alix, Léa, Lucy, and the rest of the cheerleading team. To Elliott, Sona, Lorna, Léo, Debbie, Sana, Charlotte, the chronic gossipers group chat and the &discord friends who heard me whine about my thesis for months, I love you all. To all the other people I have carved a place for in my heart, thank you all for making this year a little easier with each laughter.

As for the people closest to me, my family by blood and by choice, I am always truly, deeply grateful for your love and unconditional support. Thank you particularly to my grandparents. My mum and dad have always been a shoulder I could lean on when I got tired, and they always encouraged me in pursuing my dreams. I would not have come all this way without them. To my best friends Victor and Esther, I just want to thank you for always loving me the way I am. You are my biggest support system and these past years would have been so much duller without you. To my childhood friends Adèle and Juliette, I am so happy that we've grown up side by side, and that our long-standing friendship has brought us to see this milestone together.

Lastly to my forever best friend, my sister Léonie: this thesis is dedicated to you. There are no words in any language that can convey how grateful I feel towards you. I could not have come this far without you by my side.

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INTRODUCTION

“I am not the law, but I represent justice so far as my feeble powers go” says Sherlock Holmes in ‘The Three Gables’ in *The Case-Book of Sherlock Holmes* (118). This quote encapsulates the unique moral position occupied by Holmes throughout the canon. He is not a legal authority, yet he often acts as a mediator between crime and justice. As one reads through the numerous Sherlock Holmes stories, a recurring theme emerges: the pursuit of justice. Where there is a crime, there is often Holmes, intervening not necessarily on behalf of the law, but in the name of a higher, sometimes more personal, sense of justice. Interestingly, Arthur Conan Doyle, the author behind this iconic character, had no formal ties to the legal world. And yet, through Holmes, he constructs a narrative universe where justice is both questioned and redefined, sometimes aligning with the law, sometimes standing outside of it.

Doyle was born in 1859 to Irish parents - Charles Doyle and Mary Doyle née Foley - in Edinburgh. Doyle attended several Jesuits schools in his childhood, both in England and in Austria. Eventually in 1876, he started attending the University of Edinburgh Medical School (Stashower 17). There, he studied medicine, and encountered Dr Joseph Bell, often acknowledged as his inspiration for the character of Sherlock Holmes. The medical background of his narrator Dr Watson was undoubtedly also heavily influenced by this part of his life. While he only studied medicine, and not law, Doyle probably would have known some of it, as was acceptable for a man of his status, but he would not have been a specialist. Regardless of Doyle’s own limited legal expertise, his writing was inevitably shaped by the legal and moral questions that animated Victorian society.

The second half of the nineteenth century was a period of great debates when it came to law and rights. Many new courts were created or reformed such as the High Court of Justice established in 1875 by the Supreme Court of Judicature Act 1873, which deals with important cases of civil law. Another instance would be the Appellate Jurisdiction Acts of 1876 and 1887 which transferred the appellate functions of the House of Lords to an Appellate Committee. There was additionally a lot of anxiety surrounding the state of the British Empire. Queen Victoria was getting older, the Empire was losing power all around the globe and was objectively less powerful than it had been. As Brendon argues, "faith in the Empire's manifest destiny, [...] at the conclusion of Queen Victoria's reign, was far from being secure" (257). This sentiment was accompanied by "anxiety about decline, in the economic as well as the political sphere" (198). One of the growing challenges the Empire was facing was rejection of its authority by the colonies. An example of that is the Second Boer War (1899–1902). Conan Doyle's vocal support for the British cause in his pamphlet *The War in South Africa* reflects contemporary anxieties about imperial decline in this sense as well. Added to that was the fact that a lot of the momentum the country had gained from the industrial revolution had been lost. Patrick O'Brien talks of "slower growth and declining shares in global industrial output and trade" in his article 'Imperialism and the Rise and Decline of the British Economy, 1688-1989'. Overall it is reasonable to say there was a generalised anxiety about what was to come next. New ways of thinking were constantly emerging, whether on different aspects of morals or on societal expectation, or even prejudice and social status. When combined with the still very high rates of crime at the time (McDonald 407), it makes sense that many people would have, on one hand, felt insecure about the

environment in which they lived, and on the other hand, wished to perhaps seek comfort in fictional stories - such as the *Sherlock Holmes* works.

In 1893, when Arthur Conan Doyle killed the detective at the Reichenbach Falls, “twenty thousand people cancelled their subscriptions” to *The Strand* (Stashower 149). This proves how Doyle’s character was deeply loved by its readership. Whatever may be the reasons behind this craze surrounding the character of Holmes and his adventures, this idea of justice being served in the stories cannot be ignored. In this case, it seems natural to wonder as to why. When it comes to crime, and therefore its punishment, there is often an intricate link to morals and ethics. If law and justice come hand in hand, so do the societal influences surrounding them. Like Lee Horsley explains in *Twentieth Century Crime Fiction*, it is entirely possible to look at crime fiction, and thus Sherlock Holmes with the assumption that “crime fiction did say something about contemporary society and did have a role to play in socio-political critique” (Horsley 6). Thus, it is evident that Sherlock Holmes serves a role in the late-Victorian society, but exactly which one? Through his detective work, Holmes offers a certain peace of mind to its reader when it comes to crime and mystery. So how exactly, through the portrayal of law, morals and the overall idea of justice, does Sherlock Holmes serve as a way to maintain social order?

With fifty-two stories in the Sherlock Holmes canon, a comprehensive study is unfeasible. Yet, what makes many of them fascinating is precisely their variety in narrative resolution and their differing portrayals of justice. To highlight this diversity, I have selected three cases - two short stories and one novel - which each present a unique way of resolving the mystery. ‘The Adventure of the Speckled Band’ and ‘The Man with the Twisted Lip’ were both published in the 1892 collection *The Adventures of Sherlock Holmes*. ‘The Speckled Band’ takes place in 1883 and follows the

character of Helen Stoker, a soon-to-be-married young lady living with her step-father, Dr Roylott. Helen Stoker consults Holmes as she fears for her life, especially since the death of her twin sister Julia, just before her wedding. 'The Man with the Twisted Lip', takes place in 1889. The story starts with Watson visiting an opium den, looking for the husband of his wife's friend Kate Whitney. There, he runs into Holmes, who has been investigating the disappearance of Neville St Clair. The third work of the corpus is the famous Sherlock Holmes novel *The Hound of the Baskervilles*. Dr James Mortimer comes to Sherlock Holmes at the beginning and tells him of a legend that has run in the Baskerville family for over 200 years. The legend speaks of a gigantic hound haunting Dartmoor and causing the early death of members of the Baskerville family. After the recent death of Sir Charles Baskerville, Dr Mortimer seeks Holmes as he is worried about Sir Charles's nephew and inheritor Sir Henry, who is arriving from Canada to Baskerville Hall.

These three stories provide a compelling lens through which to examine how Holmes enacts justice, or perhaps more precisely, how he constructs and restores a version of social order that reassures readers. Through their treatment of crime, punishment, and morality, these narratives reflect broader cultural anxieties and ideologies of the late-Victorian period.

This study will therefore explore how the figure of Sherlock Holmes negotiates the boundaries between legal justice, moral comfort, and societal control, and whether the order he restores is as stable and inclusive as it seems. The first part will examine the detective's relationship to official legal institutions. The second part will focus on the moral framework underlying Holmes's decisions and its limits. Finally, the third part will explore how his actions maintain or challenge broader systems of social order and imperial ideology.

PART I - LEGAL LANDSCAPE OF LATE-VICTORIAN ENGLAND

A - The law: New bills, Reforms and Newborn Justice

In order to fully understand exactly how crime and morals are represented in the Sherlock Holmes novels and how they mirror the society in which the author, Arthur Conan Doyle, lived, one must understand firstly how law functioned at the time. Indeed, there is an intrinsic link between the state of law in the last two decades of the nineteenth century and how crimes in stories are not only represented but also punished.

One of the most important ways in which law is portrayed in the Sherlock Holmes canon is through property and financial inheritance. In a paper by Stephen R. Alton, depicting a fake manuscript of a never-discovered-before Sherlock Holmes story, the character of Watson says to Holmes: “entailments and inheritances lay in the background in several of the problems on which you have consulted. Most famously, there was the case of *The Hound of the Baskervilles*” (Alton 168). Undeniably, when thinking of property transfer in the canon, *The Hound of the Baskervilles* is the one story that comes to mind. While a considerable part of the plot revolves around the secret identity of Jack Stapleton, it also revolves around his rights to Baskerville Hall as a family member.

What causes the biggest problem in *The Hound of the Baskervilles*, is inheritance of the property of Baskerville Hall as well as the considerable Baskerville fortune. As Dr Mortimer, the witness to Sir Charles' will, explains to Holmes at the beginning of the story, it is supposed that Sir Charles' brother, Sir Rodger, died without a next of kin. However, Holmes explains in Chapter 15 "A Retrospection" that "[Stapleton] was a son of that Rodger Baskerville, the younger brother of Sir Charles, who fled with a sinister reputation to South America, where he was said to have died unmarried. He did, as a matter of fact, marry, and had one child, this fellow, whose real name is the same as his father's." (*Hound* 167).

The main issue in *The Hound of the Baskervilles* resides in the uncertainty of whether or not Sir Henry is indeed the sole heir, or at the very least the first in line to inherit both the property and the money of the Baskerville family.

At the time at which the story takes place - while the text does not provide an exact year, it would be in the second half of the 1880s - the law regarding inheritance and primogeniture was still the same one that had existed in England since 1285 with the Statute of Westminster II. "[T]his rule remained unchanged in England, even in the second half of the nineteenth century - Holmes's own day" (136) explains Alton. The law on fee tail was only abolished in England in 1925, a couple of decades after the writing of *The Hound of the Baskervilles*, with the Law of Property Act. The fee tail male that we see in *The Hound of the Baskervilles*, i.e. "an estate that the male line inherited according to the English rules of primogeniture, with the eldest son of the eldest son inheriting" (Alton 135), would imply that only Sir Charles' eldest son would inherit the Baskerville fortune. As he did not have children, the next in line would be his younger brother Rodger, and lastly the youngest brother Henry. It is originally assumed that Rodger died childless, and thus Sir Henry the son, is the closest in line

to inherit. Stapleton turning out to be Sir Rodger's son, and thus closer in line to inheritance compared to Sir Henry, does not solve everything. Indeed, in the case Sir Rodger had sired Stapleton outside of marriage, he would not have any rights over the Baskerville inheritance. This is explained by Alton as well: "[t]he incapacity of a bastard consists principally in this, that he cannot be heir to any one, neither can he have heirs, but of his own body, being *nullius filius*, he is therefore of kin to nobody, and has no ancestor from whom any inheritable blood can be derived" (136).

With all these elements, it appears clearer than ever how in *The Hound of the Baskervilles*, legal matters, here in particular inheritance, play a crucial part in the story.

It honestly seems coherent that legal matters would be at the centre of so many Sherlock Holmes stories. As Alton explains, "[t]hat Sherlock Holmes was well acquainted with the field of donative transfers is not particularly surprising, given his vast store of knowledge in so many diverse areas." (125). In the first novel of the canon, *A Study in Scarlet*, Holmes is seen "glancing at a seventeenth century legal treatise, *De Jure inter Gentes*", literally meaning 'of the Law between people'. (Alton 131) Madeline B. Stern qualifies the book as one of the many extraordinary literary pieces Holmes possesses, and explains that it is a very real book: "*De Jure inter Gentes*, though published anonymously, was really written by Richard Zouche (1590-1661), the English civilian" (134). She adds that "[i]n a way, the 1642 Zouche is [...] an even more interesting volume. Indeed, had Thomas James Wise evinced any interest in international law in the year 1881, one might almost be ready to accuse him of perpetrating the work in question" (135). This proves that despite the age of the book, the ideas that it presented were still very modern at the time Doyle

started writing Sherlock Holmes. This propulses the work into a dimension of social criticism, or at the very least places it in a context of intellectual continuity between early legal humanism and late-Victorian anxieties about justice.

On top of that, the changing legal landscape at the time would have offered Doyle many opportunities to use the law as a plot device. This, for example, can be seen in 'The Adventure of the Speckled Band'. As aforementioned, this short story was originally published in 1891, but the story takes place in 1883: "It was early in April, in the year '83" (*Adventures* 171). In 1882 and 1883 passed two important acts regarding women, inheritance and their right to property. Firstly in 1882, a second Married Women's Property Act entitled married women to retain separate ownership of any property they owned before marriage. Before this bill, a woman's property would be legally passed into the ownership of her husband as soon as they were wed. The following year - the year in which 'The Speckled Band' takes place, married women obtained the right to acquire their own property. These two bills demonstrate how law at the time was changing to accommodate the situation of married and unmarried women who were acquiring more rights. It seems telling that Doyle decided to set this particular short story in 1883, in the middle of this changing legal context.

In 'The Adventure of the Speckled Band', Helen Stoker comes to consult Holmes as she fears for her life. As she explains to Holmes when they first meet: "in a month or two I shall be married, with the control of my own income" (*Hound* 173). This part would not have been possible had the story taken place only a couple of years prior, which is why the legal context to the story is so crucial. Eventually, Holmes uncovers the truth: the stepfather, Dr Roylott, murdered one of the twin sisters, Julia, and is planning to strike again against Helen. It turns out that when the sisters' mother

passed away, she arranged for her husband to receive an income until the daughters married. If one daughter married, he would still receive half of the annual income, and “[i]f both daughters married, Roylott would be entirely divested of his annual income under his late wife’s will. However, her legacy had been written in such a way that Roylott’s life income would not terminate if the daughters were to die without having married.” (Alton 165). This is the motive behind the murder of Julia and the attempted murder of Helen. Once again, it is clear how inheritance issues serve as a plot device for the crime to be committed in the story - and thus that law is a core part of it as well.

To conclude on this matter, it is abundantly clear by now that Arthur Conan Doyle used inheritance issues in his works as the motivation for the crime, and as the resolution of the case. This indicates the importance of legal matters in not only his life, but very likely the life of most property owners of the late nineteenth century. New bills were being introduced, causing important changes for property owners, including women earning more rights. These significant changes are well reflected in the Sherlock Holmes canon — not only in the selected works here, but as mentioned by Alton, in many other stories such as ‘The Adventure of the Three Garridebs’, ‘The Adventure of the Copper Beeches’ or ‘The Adventure of the Missing Three-Quarter’ among many others. The very first link between law in Sherlock Holmes and late-Victorian society is now evident.

But Holmes does not only use the law, he also is the law in a way. As Clive Emsley points out in *Crime and Society*, legal representation in criminal matters remained rare and financially inaccessible well into the early twentieth century: “In 1851 it was argued in the *Law Times* that the state had a duty to allow or assign counsel to

prisoners who could not afford them, but it was not until the Poor Prisoner's Defence Act 1903 that any significant move was made in this direction." (Emsley 201). In this context, Sherlock Holmes can be seen not merely as a symbol of detection, but as a necessary surrogate to an unreliable and exclusionary legal system. His interventions offer clients not only resolution but also access to a form of justice that the institutional framework could not always provide.

This is particularly relevant in light of the procedural norms of the time. Minor offences were frequently handled through summary trials, where no jury was required and a confession could be sufficient to issue a sentence. Confessions played a central role in the Victorian criminal justice system. A voluntary confession, particularly one made before arrest or without coercion, was often sufficient to bypass a full trial. In David Bentley's book *English Criminal Justice in the 19th Century*, he explains that "magistrates [were] shutting the mouth of a prisoner when he began to volunteer a confession by advising him not to commit himself." (31) He also says that "the law [...] rigorously excluded hearsay, involuntary confession and evidence of the accused's bad character" (205), implying that voluntary confession was considered evidence in a trial. In the second half of the century, like Bentley explains, summary trials grew exponentially, so much that "by 1900 over 98 per cent of all criminal trials were summary." (19)

With this in mind, Holmes appears not just as an instrument of narrative logic, but as a fictional embodiment of justice itself. He offers what the law often could not: investigation, deliberation, and resolution. Far from merely solving mysteries, Holmes represents a substitute moral authority, stepping in where institutions prove unreliable or exclusionary.

In both 'The Speckled Band' and *The Hound of the Baskervilles*, the story deals with important crimes - murder and attempted murder - and in any case, both Dr Roylott and Stapleton eventually meet their end. Their death, of course, makes any possibility of a trial vanish. However, when it comes to St Clair in 'The Man with the Twisted Lip', the situation is different. Under the 1824 Vagrancy Act, individuals could be arrested simply for begging, regardless of their behaviour or intentions. Technically, Neville St Clair as Hugh Boone, should have been prosecuted for public begging. And indeed, he is arrested by the police.

'Yes. He was brought up and remanded for further inquiries.'
'So I heard. You have him here?'
'In the cells.'
(*Adventures*, 142)

Yet once Holmes uncovers his identity and motives, he is quietly released. The justification is not legal, but moral: St Clair is not truly poor, and he has not committed what Holmes considers a real crime. This response echoes the logic of summary trials, where dismissive justice was often dispensed based on social standing and confessions, without deeper inquiry: "There was also much press complaint [...] about the rudeness of magistrates towards the poor and defenceless (Bentley 28). Holmes, while more discerning than the law, unconsciously upholds the same principle, meaning social standing determines culpability. Justice, in this case, is reserved not for those who break the law but for those who look like they belong outside it.

Holmes's ability to elicit confessions thus aligns with a broader legal tendency to favour speed and clarity over courtroom theatrics, reinforcing the idea that narrative closure can substitute legal formality.

B - Offenses in the Holmes Canon

Talking about law in media often necessitates one to also consider how that law punishes criminals. The reason for selecting the three different stories under study is mainly because of the opposite outcomes for the “criminals” regarding different factors: the crime that has - or not - been committed, as well as the social standing of the perpetrator.

To understand in detail how crime is depicted in the Sherlock Holmes canon and its consequences, it is necessary to first look at crime in the late-Victorian Londonian world, and how it was punished.

In the collective mind, nineteenth-century England is often associated with extreme poverty and high crime rates. While this is mainly influenced by famous fiction works like the ones of Charles Dickens, it may have been rooted in truth. This is explained by Pamela Makati in *A Critical Study of Charles Dickens' Representation of the Socially Disadvantaged*: “[F]rom childhood, all that the poor are exposed to is crime. Therefore, members of the lower class are stereotyped as criminals from an early age, who take many trips in and out of courts and the prison.” (15). Many have argued before that this representation of important crime rates is rooted in truth. Christopher Clausen, in ‘Sherlock Holmes, Order and the Late-Victorian Mind’, mentions a “growth of poverty and social unrest that followed the industrial revolution” (111). On the other hand, Lynn McDonald explains in her paper ‘Theory and Evidence of Rising Crime in the Nineteenth Century’ that it may not have been

the case. She notably cites V.A.C Gatrell and T.B Hadden's work *Criminal Statistics and their interpretation*.

"If the actual level of criminal activity had remained stable or even marginally declined, it is reasonable to expect increasing efficiency of the police and the courts would have led to an increase in the number of recorded offences and committals. Therefore the fact that there was a substantial *decrease* in the recorded rates is particularly significant: the figures must reflect a real decline in criminal activity, and quite a spectacular one." (Gatrell and Hadden 314)
(406)

This argument made by McDonald exposes two important aspects of crime in the nineteenth century. Firstly, while it may have appeared that the rates were quite high in the 1830s until the 1860s, it seems that this was only the case because more criminals were apprehended following an upgrade of the police and courts of law's efficiency. The decrease in crime in the second half of the century only accentuated this phenomenon.

Lynn McDonald provides in her paper a chart (Chart I 407) showing the serious offenses in England and Wales between 1805 and 1892. This graph clearly illustrates an important decline of both male and female committals from the 1860s onwards.

With this data, it is clear that, while there had been a decline overall in crime in the last decades of the nineteenth century, it had been perceived as high in the prior years. This, of course, would have caused continued anxiety to the inhabitants of London, who had experienced fear of crime for a long time. In any event, as explained in 'Fictions of Crime, and Purified Reading Communities' by Christopher Pittard, "[b]y the 1890s, roughly 55% of prisoners were repeat offenders, rising to 65-75% in the Edwardian era. This figure was seen both as a criticism of the penal system and as evidence for the existence of professional criminals [...]." (8). With

this, it is consistent that crime was still a central issue at the turn of the century, with a majority of criminals being repeat offenders.

How exactly do these high occurrences of crime translate into fiction? Similarly to many other literary genres, and as it has always been, authors often infuse reality into their work. In Sherlock Holmes, just like the *fin-de-siècle* London, crime is a common event.

An examination of the three stories is first necessary, in order to recap the crimes and punishments that are depicted. In the instance a crime has been committed, it is only natural for the reader to expect the criminal to be punished.

In *The Hound of the Baskervilles*, the crime is very straightforward: the murder of Sir Charles by Stapleton, like Holmes reveals in Chapter 13, "Fixing the nets": "We regard this case as one of murder, and the evidence may implicate not only your friend Mr. Stapleton but his wife as well." (150).

The death penalty had existed in England well before the nineteenth century, with accounts going back as far as Henry VII's reign. In 1828 was passed an Offenses Against the Person Act, dubbed by Gregory Thomas Smith as "[t]he first truly comprehensive piece of legislation designed to address interpersonal violence in British society" (58). This Act was followed by a second one in 1861 (24 & 25 Vict. c. 94 to c. 100) which limited civilian capital crimes in England and Wales to only five, one of them being murder. Capital punishment in England was later abolished in 1969, and thus at the time in which *The Hound of the Baskervilles* takes place, death by hanging would be the expected punishment for Stapleton. However, as Watson concludes in Chapter 14 "The Hound of the Baskervilles", he assumes Jack Stapleton eventually met his end in the moor: "If the earth told a true story, then

Stapleton never reached that island of refuge towards which he struggled through the fog upon that last night. Somewhere in the heart of the great Grimpen Mire, down in the foul slime of the huge morass which had sucked him in, this cold and cruel-hearted man is forever buried.” (*Hound* 164).

This ending is ambivalent. If one sticks to the version told by Holmes and Watson, it can be explained that Jack Stapleton is punished through death because he comes from a line of evil men, and he himself committed evil through the murder of his uncle and the attempted murder of his cousin. To that can be added the fact that had he been caught, his punishment would have been death no matter what.

However, many scholars have contested the ending regarding Stapleton’s death, and argue it is possible that Stapleton did get away: “Stapleton vanishes at the end, it is assumed to his death, but there is no real material proof that he is dead” (Pennington 141). Nonetheless, even if Stapleton did die, he also did get away at first. Neither Holmes and Watson, nor Lestrade - representing Scotland Yard and thus the police force - are able to catch him. Whether or not Stapleton’s death is materially confirmed, the narrative ultimately frames it as a form of retribution. He is swallowed by the landscape he tried to manipulate, thus ensuring that the criminal is punished, if not by the hand of justice, then by nature itself.

Regarding ‘The Adventure of the Speckled Band’, the end that Dr Roylott meets is similar to Stapleton’s. Indeed, just like him, Roylott’s main crime is to have murdered his step-daughter Julia and to have attempted to kill her sister Helen as well. However, we also learn from the book that Dr Roylott has had violent tendencies for a long time, and that he killed his servant when he lived in India. This is explained by Helen Stoker herself during her first encounter with Holmes: “he beat his native butler to death, and narrowly escaped a capital sentence.” (*Adventures* 175). In the

end, Dr Roylott dies in a painful manner, killed by the snake he trained - a snake so poisonous it kills its prey almost instantly: “the deadliest snake in India. He has died within ten seconds of being bitten” (*Adventures* 195). Conan Doyle himself often referred to ‘The Adventure of the Speckled Band’ as his favourite Sherlock Holmes novel. In 1927, *The Strand* - the magazine publishing the Sherlock Holmes stories - released a list of the favourite short stories of Arthur Conan Doyle himself. This was explained in the notes by Richard Lancelyn Green in the Oxford World’s Classics edition of *The Adventures of Sherlock Holmes*: “ACD referred to the story as a ‘thriller’ in a letter to his mother in Oct. 1891 and considered it the best of the series. [...] It was placed first on his list of the twelve best stories” (*Adventures* 362). All of these elements point towards the fact that the way Dr Roylott is eventually punished for his crimes is not something Arthur Conan Doyle would have skipped over lightly. As aforementioned, when Helen Stoker explains the story of her step-father to Holmes and Watson, she tells them that he almost got the capital punishment for the murder of his butler. He escaped justice, and due to his violent and greedy tendencies, stroke again. In the end, as Holmes says “Violence does, in truth, recoil upon the violent” (*Adventures* 196). In this case, justice is served through the death of the villain; just like the court would have likely decided for Dr Roylott to be hanged, the murderer cannot get away from dying.

When it comes to ‘The Man with the Twisted Lip’, the case is different. In this short story, the plot twist reveals that Hugh Boone is in fact, Neville St Clair. Under British Law at the time, the only crime St Clair has committed is begging. St Clair did not commit theft, nor did he usurp the identity of someone else, nor did Hugh Boone murder St Clair like Holmes first suspects. For the majority of the story, Holmes

thinks he is investigating not a mystery but solving a crime: the murder of Neville St Clair. Eventually, the mystery turns out to be simply a lie between spouses. This story concludes with St Clair being released from custody. The police officer makes him promise to not take on the identity of Hugh Boone again: "If the police are to hush this thing up, there must be no more of Hugh Boone." (*Adventures* 147). In this case, a court of law would have been useless. Holmes himself, despite his apparently vast knowledge of the law, does not consider St Clair's actions as punishable by state justice: "No crime, but a very great error has been committed", said Holmes" (*Adventures* 144). However, from a moral standpoint, St Clair's actions can be criticised. It is known that St Clair is in fact a rich man of good social standing: "My father was a schoolmaster in Chesterfield, where I received a good education" (*Adventures* 145). His resorting to a professional beggar business was originally done to repay a debt, but he kept going even after it was over. Given the social standing of Neville St Clair, it is very likely that he is not shamed for his job for that reason. Had it been a character from a poorer or less prestigious background, the ending may have been different.

In this case, it can be argued that there is once again, a link between the backstory and virtue of the "villain" or "antagonist" character and his punishment.

Just as Christopher Clausen explains "Order, if not always law, is upheld [...] because the crime was a pardonable act of revenge for acts that the law was helpless to redress[...]" (113). One of the examples of this is "The Man with the Twisted Lip".

All in all, these elements show how crime was still a prevalent issue in the very late Victorian period, and how that transpired into the Sherlock Holmes stories. It is once

again made clear how reality influenced the plot of the works, and how law and justice are a core part of the Sherlock Holmes canon.

C - The Poor and the Foreigner

To understand how justice functions in Conan Doyle's stories, it is crucial to examine how it reflects or challenges the class hierarchies and social divisions that structured Victorian society.

David Cody, professor of English at Hartwick College, defines the notion of classes in nineteenth-century British society as the "distinct social groupings which at any given historical period, taken as a whole, constituted British Society. [They are] distinguished by inequalities in such areas as power, authority, wealth, working and living conditions, life-styles, life-span, education, religion, and culture." (*Victorian Web Social Class*). Kwasi Kwarteng also mentions this aspect of nineteenth-century British society in his book *Ghosts of Empire*. He says that "the key to understanding the British Empire is the idea of natural hierarchy. Class and status were absolutely integral to the empire" (391). This allows a first insight into the British society of the nineteenth century, one that is known to have been heavily divided by class inequalities, and exacerbated by matters of gender and ethnicity particularly.

When it comes to Sherlock Holmes, it can be assumed that certain characters may face more prejudice in the case of a crime because of the class they belong to, or on the contrary, benefit from privilege. This would be corroborated by deeply common Victorian ideas that foreigners, the poor and other discriminated classes were inherently violent. In *The Races of Britain* (1885), John Beddoe emphasised the vast difference between the protruding and less prominent jaws of the people of Britain. It was generally assumed that lower class people as well as foreigners were among

the protruding category - closer to apes. "The English governing classes in the 1860's regarded the Irish and the non-European 'native' peoples just as they had, quite openly, regarded their own labouring classes for many centuries: as thoroughly undisciplined, with a tendency to revert to bestial behaviour" (Semmel 135). In *The Hound of the Baskervilles*, the character of Sir Charles is worth paying attention to. It is known that Sir Charles spent some time abroad in South Africa, and that is where an important part of the Baskerville fortune comes from. This is explained by Sir Hugo in the second chapter 'The Curse of the Baskervilles': "Sir Charles, as is well known, made large sums of money in South African speculation" (*Hound* 13). While Africa is perceived as a faraway place, slightly exotic, in this instance it is associated with something positive: money. It is explained in particular that outside of the inheritance that belongs to Sir Henry, and the sum of money reserved for the Barrymores, Sir Charles decided before his death to donate large amounts of his fortune to charities: "There were many insignificant sums to individuals, and a large number of public charities. The residue all went to Sir Henry." (*Hound* 45). This shows the moral character of Sir Charles, who donated part of his wealth, and demonstrates his privileged status as a white rich philanthropic man. Thus, in this case, the victim, Sir Charles, is portrayed in a positive light, despite the controversial presence of Africa in the equation.

On the opposite side, as the villain, is Jack Stapleton. Stapleton is the son of Sir Rodger Baskerville, who "fled with a sinister reputation to South America" (*Hound* 167). In this situation, Doyle is clearly criticising the attitude of Sir Rodger, but also drawing a parallel between his perturbed personality and going to a distant, exotic but underdeveloped place. There, Sir Rodger married Stapleton's mother. Stapleton's moral character here is heavily linked with the exotic elements attributed

to his parents. Evidently, his father already had an ill reputation before leaving England, but the specific choice of fleeing for such a far-away place as Central America furthers this image. This, coupled with the fact that his mother is herself from this remote, perhaps even savage, place, is directly linked to the representation of his morals in the story.

This creates a parallel between Sir Charles and Stapleton. On one side is an old philanthropist, the perfect image of the rich white gentleman from the countryside, and on the other is his nephew, morals tainted by his foreign origins.

It can be concluded thus that this link between instance of birth and moral character plays a great deal into the resolution of the case. The victim is white and rich, whereas the murderer is associated with a foreign place, making it a violent realm, and furthermore reinforcing the idea that foreigners were dangerous.

When it comes to 'The Adventure of the Speckled Band', one very clear aspect of discrimination when it comes to the case is striking. In this short story, the first trail that Holmes decides to follow in order to figure out the truth behind the death of Julia Stoker, is the presence of travellers near the estate where Dr Roylott and Helen Stoker live. "When you combine the ideas of whistles at night, the presence of a band of gipsies who are on intimate terms with this old doctor, [...] I think that there is good ground to think that the mystery may be cleared along those lines." (*Adventures* 182). In the Victorian era there existed a particular bias towards different traveller groups in Great Britain - whether Irish, Roma or another group - who were viewed with suspicion. It is said that "[t]hey had a reputation for fraudulent transactions, pickpocketing and thieving, and making unsightly and inconvenient roadside stops." (*Victorian Web 'Gypsies, Roma or Travellers'*). In this instance,

Holmes' own typically-Victorian racial bias is apparent as he immediately suspects the group of travellers living near Stoke Moran before having any hard evidence that they could be linked to the death of Julia Stoker.

However, the presence of racial discrimination in this short story goes further than this, adding an additional layer to the wicked personality of Dr Roylott. Many parallels between him and exoticism are drawn. The first, and most obvious, is Helen's explanation behind her step-father's temperament. She says "[v]iolence of temper [...] has been hereditary in the men of the family, and in my stepfather's case [...] intensified by his long residence in the tropics." (*Adventures* 175) As explained previously, it was a common misconception in the Victorian era that travelling to the colonies and interacting excessively with people of colour would change your personality – or at least many people used it as an argument to justify their actions. Rosemary Jann explains this attitude very well. She says that "[f]oreigners are always treated as exotics by Doyle, as if to imply that the infection of British normalcy is more plausible when it comes from exposure to alien contagions" (Jann 76). Nonetheless, Dr Roylott's despicable traits do not stop there. Helen explains to Holmes how her step-father, while he was in Calcutta, "beat his native butler to death" (*Adventures* 175), yet escaped the death penalty. It is obvious that Dr Roylott murdered the man because he felt superior rather than any formal motive. The last point to be made about Dr Roylott and how he is portrayed is his affinity for exotic animals. This is explained by Helen to Holmes: "He has a passion for Indian animals" (*Adventures* 176). This sentence once again strengthens the parallel that is drawn between Dr Roylott, the antagonist and villain of the story, with exoticism. Furthermore, the snake that will later be revealed to be the weapon of Julia's murder, also draws a parallel between exoticism and murder. All these elements only

reinforce the mindset of many during the *fin-de-siècle* that the colonies were unruly places, filled with crime. Therefore, the people who came from the colonies or spent time there could be dangerous.

Regarding the third story, 'The Man with the Twisted Lip', there are also elements of racial prejudice that can be observed. When Watson heads for the opium den, he mentions a "sallow Malay attendant" beckoning him into the shop (*Adventures* 125). Historically, most of the opium dens in London were run by the Chinese community. Dickens notably is famous for his portrayal of an opium den in East London in his unfinished work *The Mystery of Edwin Drood*, which is suspected to have been inspired by a real-life den run by a Chinese man, Ah Sing: "Jack Chinaman t'other side of the court" (*Edwin Drood* 2). However, Holmes also mentions that he cannot trust "the rascally Lascar who runs [the den]." Lascar was then mostly used to refer to Indian sailors, meaning that in the case of this short story, the den is not Chinese-owned. Unlike in 'The Speckled Band', Holmes' first instinct is not to suspect the clients of the den, nor the owner. Nonetheless, the accent on their foreign origins does put into question a more vague link to crime in general. Indeed, people of colour were often compared to members of the lower classes; both were seen as criminal, filthy and inhabitants of unknown dark lands or territories (*Race and Class Overview: Parallels in Racism and Class Prejudice*). This is seconded by Worthington, who explains that "[...] Chinese or Indian figures were sometimes used as a secondary, background element, functioning to suggest or invoke criminality, mystery, corruption, deviant sexuality, exotic drugs or simply to create atmosphere." (112) In this instance, it appears clear that Doyle uses the exotic feelings invoked by

the presence of Asian characters to accentuate the dangerous atmosphere surrounding the opium den.

But exactly why would this place be so dangerous? The opium den in the story is situated on Swandam Lane, a fictitious place. But as explained previously, most opium dens in the nineteenth century were situated in the East End of London - a place of ill-repute for it was a slum. Therefore, it can be imagined that the fake opium den from the story is also situated in this particularly poor neighbourhood - and even more so as it is described as a "vile alley" (*Adventure* 125). Anthony S. Wohl, Professor at Vassar College in New York, says that in the nineteenth century, the perception of poor people was such that it was heavily linked to crime and delinquency: "It is enacted by a society which increasingly condemns the poor as products of their own low and immoral natures. They are indolent, ignorant, degraded, fraudulent — pervasive language is one of criminality and anti-social behaviour." (Victorian Web *Perception of the Poor: Criminality*). Therefore, not only are the poor associated with being criminals, but most people also assumed the poor wanted to be poor. This relates heavily with the plot of 'The Man with the Twisted Lip'. It is unveiled eventually that Hugh Boone is Neville St Clair, who purposely chose to become a professional beggar in order to reimburse a debt. This double identity of a gentleman versus a beggar creates a discrepancy in values and moral perception. The fact itself that St Clair would pass as a poor person could possibly establish a portrait of his moral standing: if one is poor then therefore they may very well be a criminal. If a respectable white man passes as a beggar, therefore he may not be so far removed from crime as it first appears. In theory, this would translate in the punishment received by St Clair - as seen with the two previous stories.

In light of the elements explored in this section, it becomes clear that Arthur Conan Doyle's work is not simply a collection of detective stories but also a dense and multi-layered reflection of the ideological and legal preoccupations of his time. The references to class, ethnicity and degeneration that permeate stories such as *The Hound of the Baskervilles*, 'The Adventure of the Speckled Band', and 'The Man with the Twisted Lip' are not incidental but fundamental in anchoring the Holmes canon within the legal landscape of the late Victorian era. In these narratives, crime is often traced back to class defect, amplified by contact with "foreign" or lower-class environments. Criminals, in these tales, are frequently portrayed as outsiders, whether by birth, geography, or class, and Doyle draws heavily on the language and assumptions of social discourses of the time to give those representations a sense of legitimacy.

If Doyle's narratives reflect the legal anxieties of Victorian Britain, they also actively participate in reinforcing or questioning the dominant values of the era. Through recurring references to class, morality, and the expected roles of individuals in society, the Sherlock Holmes stories serve as a lens through which Victorian ideals are both staged and scrutinised.

PART II -

VICTORIAN VALUES: CLASS, MORALITY AND SOCIAL ROLE

A- Victorian London as a Life-Size Panopticon

If criminality was, in part, constructed through systems of categorisation and exclusion, it was also shaped by the development of increasingly sophisticated mechanisms of control. As society moved away from public, spectacular punishment, power began to operate in more invisible, internalised ways.

In *Discipline and Punish: The Birth of the Prison*, Michel Foucault examines the transformation of societal power structures, highlighting the shift from overt, corporeal punishment to subtle, pervasive forms of surveillance. *Discipline and Punish* presents the shifts in power structures and societal norms that led to changes in penal systems. He builds this analysis in particular on Jeremy Bentham's invention of the panopticon. Originally designed in the 18th century, the panopticon is an institutional building - prison, asylum, hospital - architectural design meant to have a single person watch the inmates. It is physically impossible for one person to have surveillance over everyone, but the system is built upon the idea that the inmates cannot know when and if they are being watched. This situation creates constant pressure and motivates them to act as though they are all being watched at all times.

Michel Foucault uses Bentham's panopticon as a metaphor for society, and applies its concepts to real life societal dynamics. He says that "[t]he Panopticon [...] must be understood as a generalizable model of functioning" (Foucault 205).

Foucault explains that the panopticon "is a type of location of bodies in space, of distribution of individuals in relation to one another, of hierarchical organization [...]" (205) which immediately reminds of the many separations at play in Victorian society. Indeed, the space that bodies occupy in a panopticon prison space is reminiscent of the extremely divided city of London, fractionated into vastly different neighbourhoods. The words "distribution of individuals" also recalls these split areas of London, with extremely poor and extremely rich parts of the city sharing a space while also being as disunited and different as can be imagined. Lastly, of course, the idea of a hierarchy is reminiscent of the social class system ruling Victorian society.

However, the closest parallel between Victorian society and the panopticon lies in the realm of moral expectations. These expectations suggest that the judgment of others played a crucial role in shaping individual behaviour. People often felt as though they were under constant observation, much like the effect produced by the panopticon. The fear of moral scrutiny and social rejection exerted direct pressure on individuals, influencing the choices they made in their daily lives.

All of these elements highlight how Victorian London, in many respects, mirrors the structure and function of a panopticon.

Foucault's theories regarding the panopticon can be meaningfully applied to Victorian society through several key lenses. First and foremost, Bentham originally envisioned the panopticon as a model for prison design, directly tying it to concepts of crime, law enforcement, punishment, and moral regulation. Within this framework,

one of the most visible and influential figures is the law officer, whose presence embodies both surveillance and the enforcement of social order.

In the 19th century, the police in England underwent an important reform. In 1829 the Metropolitan Police was established to police the centre of London, followed by acts in 1835, 1839 and 1856 all expanding the presence of the police in the country. (Emsley 221) This expansion meant that police officers became a more visible and widespread force in everyday life. However, in 'Common Misperceptions', Christopher Casey relates the words of a clergyman, who in the 1860s wrote that "[t]he public have their safety to a large degree in their own hands. If the police are not able to protect us we must and will shift for ourselves", showing a distrust for the state forces.

Like Foucault explains in *Discipline and Punish*, society can be compared to the panopticon prison. So, what is the link between panopticon and Victorian society described in Doyle canon?

"The real, corporal disciplines constituted the foundation of the formal, juridical liberties.

The contract may have been regarded as the ideal foundation of law and political power; panopticism constituted the technique, universally widespread, of coercion."

(222)

This statement is complex but fundamental for understanding not only the role of the panopticon, but also the way power operates in modern societies. At first glance the starting point of Foucault's idea may seem paradoxical. What Foucault calls liberties refers to our "official" liberties (justice, rights, social contract, etc.). However these liberties are dependent on a very discreet but concrete control of bodies – which Foucault will later theorise as biopolitics. They are called liberties but constraints still exist: arrive on time at work, stay in line at school, keep postures and behaviour in

public, and many others. These daily disciplines, invisible and incorporated, are for Foucault, the true foundations of modern power, behind the pretence of law and freedom. In this quote, Foucault contrasts this to the theory of the social contract proposed by philosophers like Rousseau and Locke. The social contract explains that the State functions because there is an agreement between individuals to organise life as a community. But according to Foucault, it is not the contract that makes power work, it's the panopticon. The panopticon is an invisible form of control, one that is internalised and constant. For him, that is exactly how society functions. Modern power is not implemented through visible violence like a public execution, but through soft surveillance techniques. Inside the building, there is only a single guard. Outside, however, the police serve as an omnipresent presence, encouraging people to behave more cautiously.

What does this say when it comes to Sherlock Holmes? Holmes incarnates the idea of moral and social order. He intervenes in a society where discipline is already everywhere: in social classes, gender norms, expected behaviours, etc. In this context he does not create order, but he reaffirms it where it is endangered. He reactivates the invisible norms. An example of this is with 'The Man with the Twisted Lip'. By letting Neville St Clair go, and by not condemning him, it is motivated by the fact that St Clair still fits the image of an acceptable respectability through his social status and his gender. Holmes applies not a purely legal logic but a moral logic.

This gives way to the role of panopticon that Holmes occupies in his universe. He is all-seeing. Like Foucault explains: "Panopticism constituted the technique, universally widespread, of coercion." Holmes is a vessel of the panoptic view. Firstly, he sees all that others do not. He notices details about the body, about clothes, gestures, clues that anyone else would have dismissed. Secondly, he makes

criminals internalise the norm. Many times, the culprits confess and are submissive to his gaze. In 'The Man with the Twisted Lip', St Clair admits:

"Great heavens!" cried the inspector, "it is, indeed, the missing man. I know him from the photograph."

The prisoner turned with the reckless air of a man who abandons himself to his destiny. "Be it so," said he.

(Adventures 144)

In this instance, Sherlock Holmes does not only act therefore as a detective. He is also a disciplinary agent. His presence only restores order not through violence but by the pressure of the eye and the exposed truth.

B - "Some Freaks of Atavism"

While Victorian society was increasingly concerned with external mechanisms of control and surveillance, such as those embodied in the panopticon, there was a parallel and equally powerful anxiety about internal threats. Among these concerns, the notion of atavism emerged as a key concept linking biology and criminality. In the second half of the nineteenth century, and more particularly in the last thirty years, England saw the rise of many discussions surrounding evolution and anthropological topics in scientific spheres. Of course, a big part of this discourse had started in 1859, with the publication of *On the origins of species* by Charles Darwin. However, at the end of the century, British society was undergoing many changes, which may have prompted an influx of discourse. The early Victorian period had been a "time of relative certainty in a fixed world". (McNabb 744) When Darwin published his work on evolution, this created many questions for everyone about humanity, who they were, where they came from, etc. At the time, the British Empire was at the top of the world, with territories all over the globe, and leaders in trade, economy, military power, science and arts. In the collective mind, the "English [were] at the top of the social and racial tree." (McNabb 744). However, in the following decades, anxiety in British society was growing. This reading echoes the wider imperial anxiety of the late-Victorian period, previously discussed in the introduction. The power of the Empire was declining, and the approaching new century, combined with the aging Queen Victoria and numerous social revolutions between others, created a social uncertainty. The pre-existing structures of power and trust in the strength of British society started to collapse. Of course, this translated into the philosophy and debates

of the time, including evolution and its circumjacent topics. This constant anxiety surrounding the crumbling of British power would have indeed questioned the existing knowledge that the British race was at the top of the pyramid. Therefore, people started to heavily question what was known of evolution and thus, debates around heredity soared. A great number of scientists, such as Francis Galton (1822-1911), worked on the topic of genetic inheritance in the 1880s, bringing debates of heredity and atavism to the foreground. This growing uncertainty led little by little to the realisation that boundaries between classes were not as tight as they had appeared to be for the longest time. Crime, notably, was a central worry of many, and it is only natural that these two fields would eventually overlap: “The truth of descent with modification and recapitulation meant that we carried the past around with us. [...] This also played to the fear of permeable boundaries.” (McNabb 745).

As a man of medicine, it is very likely that, as explained by John McNabb in his paper ‘Anthropology by gaslight’, Doyle would have been actively reading medical newspapers at the time. These newspapers, such as the *British Medical Journal*, or *The Lancet*, included papers of scientific topics - a rich source of anthropological and evolutionary discourse.

In his very first Sherlock Holmes work, *A Study in Scarlet*, Arthur Conan Doyle says “I saw before me the distorted, baboon-like countenance of the murdered man. [...] If ever human features bespoke vice of the most malignant type, they were certainly those of Enoch J. Drebber of Cleveland.” In this extract, Doyle makes a clear reference to atavistic rhetoric. Based on the previous evidence provided by McNabb, it is hard to deny that these topics of anthropology, and in particular atavism, were not at the core of many scientific debates in the *fin-de-siècle*; therefore the fact that Conan Doyle included some of that rhetoric in his very first detective novel proves

how it was a focal point of his own ideology. And indeed, as shown by the data collected by McNabb, about thirty works of the Sherlock Holmes canon contain “references to evolution, human origins and other themes relevant to Victorian anthropology.” (732).

In *The Hound of the Baskervilles*, the topics of heredity and atavism are at the core of the plot, with the villain Jack Stapleton revealed to be in fact a Baskerville. The truth is uncovered by Holmes who recognises his likeness to the cruel Sir Hugo with a portrait of the latter. With the description of Stapleton, it is clear to see in which ways he has inherited Sir Hugo’s looks and his dark nature.

He stood upon a chair, and, holding up the light in his left hand, he curved his right arm over the broad hat and round the long ringlets.

“Good heavens!” I cried in amazement.

The face of Stapleton had sprung out of the canvas.

“Ha, you see it now. My eyes have been trained to examine faces and not their trimmings. It is the first quality of a criminal investigator that he should see through a disguise.”

“But this is marvellous. It might be his portrait.”

“Yes, it is an interesting instance of a throwback, which appears to be both physical and spiritual. A study of family portraits is enough to convert a man to the doctrine of reincarnation. The fellow is a Baskerville—that is evident.”

(*Hound* 146)

Like aforementioned, Doyle certainly subscribed to many ideas of his time, especially inherited criminality as seen through the voice of Sherlock Holmes. Stapleton conforms to this idea of inherited criminality, being a direct descendant of the wicked Sir Hugo Baskerville.

By the time Doyle wrote *The Hound of the Baskervilles* at the turn of the century, studies on heredity had moved on from the original theories by Lombroso but Doyle’s

portrayal of his characters plays into a more mid-Victorian scientist type. Dr Mortimer is the prime example of this in *The Hound of the Baskervilles*. The practitioner has himself written several books on atavism, as mentioned in his first meeting with Holmes and Watson.

“Mortimer, James, M.R.C.S., 1882, Grimpen, Dartmoor, Devon. House-surgeon, from 1882 to 1884, at Charing Cross Hospital. Winner of the Jackson prize for Comparative Pathology, with essay entitled ‘Is Disease a Reversion?’ Corresponding member of the Swedish Pathological Society. Author of ‘Some Freaks of Atavism’ (*Lancet* 1882). ‘Do We Progress?’ (*Journal of Psychology*, March, 1883). Medical Officer for the parishes of Grimpen, Thorsley, and High Barrow.”

(*Hound 4*)

During that first meeting, Dr Mortimer also surprises Watson and Holmes by his passion for human skulls and what they reveal of the true nature of humans.

“I had hardly expected so dolichocephalic a skull or such well-marked supra-orbital development. Would you have any objection to my running my finger along your parietal fissure? A cast of your skull, sir, until the original is available, would be an ornament to any anthropological museum. It is not my intention to be fulsome, but I confess that I covet your skull.”

(*The Hound of the Baskervilles 6*)

Through Holmes’s ability to detect atavistic traits and inherited criminal tendencies, Doyle engages with the scientific and moral debates of his time. By drawing on atavistic theories, Doyle reflects a society increasingly anxious about the blurred lines between civilisation and savagery, respectability and deviance. Rather than

suggesting that biology itself is unstable, Doyle uses Holmes to reassert control. Science and logic become tools to contain the fear that social boundaries might dissolve. In this way, Holmes doesn't just solve crimes. but helps restore a fragile sense of stability in a world unsettled by new scientific ideas.

C - The Moral Logic of Crime

With the previous part on opposition between classes and how privilege plays a role in justice, it has been established that late-Victorian and early Edwardian beliefs have an important part in the perception of crime, especially in connection to poverty and the foreign. This background of Victorian morality and values, and their association with crime raises the question of how these strict morals are represented in the story. The idea of a moral contract, crucial in a late-Victorian era directed by appearances, seems frequently tested and perhaps broken. This reflects the tensions within the social order.

In the first part, it was explained how crime was perceived in the late nineteenth century, what the consequences were, and how this translates into the three selected stories. However, in relation to this, it is necessary to also wonder exactly how late-Victorian morals exist in the context of crime in the Sherlock Holmes canon.

In the collective mind, Victorian morals are often associated with modesty, restraint, rigorous morals - for example with marriage and charity - as well as an importance of hierarchy and moderation. The Victorian moral code emphasised discipline, rationality, and a strong sense of duty, especially in the upper classes. Stephen Greenbalt, in the Introduction of the Tenth Edition of the Norton Anthology 'The Victorian Age' explains the history behind the coining of the period from the 1830s until 1901 after the name of the monarch of that period. He states that "Victoria herself encouraged her own identification with the qualities we associate with the adjective [Victorian] - earnestness, moral responsibility, domestic propriety." (5). From this it can be deduced how crime would be on the opposite of these values and

threaten them. Crime, therefore, was not seen solely as a breach of the law but also as a deviation from these moral expectations, threatening the highly-valued balance of social order. The stories of the canon explore these and their consequences, emphasising the importance of maintaining societal norms.

This Victorian morality appears in a context of rapid changes, mostly due to industrialisation and rapid urbanisation in the previous decades, which led to the birth of this controlling moral lining within a society in mutation. Of course, while not everything immoral is a crime and not all crimes are immoral, there exists an intrinsic link between the two.

In the Sherlock Holmes stories, the punishment of immoral behaviours is essential. Victorian morality was at the core of societal values and the detective novel revolving around these moral disturbances proves the importance of the canon in maintaining social order.

Two of the stories at study - *The Hound of the Baskervilles* and 'The Adventure of the Speckled Band' - deal with cases of murder. In both cases, the murder was committed for personal selfish reasons regarding money or inheritance, which Stephen Knight defines as "a crime for greed" (89). In this case, it is easy to say both of these murders were highly immoral when related to the importance of social appearances.

In 'The Man with the Twisted Lip', a gentleman becomes a beggar to gain more money. In the end, as explained above, he is not condemned. Neville St Clair's decision to abandon his status for the lure of easy wealth represents a violation of the Victorian moral code, even if he is not punished in the conventional legal sense. In allowing him to go free, it is implied that his status as well as the social order allow for forgiveness. His position in the social hierarchy, and the belief in second chances

for men of his class, provide a possibility for forgiveness that might not have been afforded a man of lower status, never mind a woman or a foreigner. Nonetheless, the high tension between social status and morals remains, making the reader wonder if social status, when regained, is enough to erase the break of the moral contract. This remaining tension is shown in the contrast in describing the appearance of Hugh Boone, immediately followed by that of Neville St Clair, now clean of his disguise.

“He was, as the inspector had said, extremely dirty, but the grime which covered his face could not conceal its repulsive ugliness. A broad weal from an old scar ran right across it from eye to chin, and by its contraction had turned up one side of the upper lip, so that three teeth were exposed in a perpetual snarl. A shock of very bright red hair grew low over his eyes and forehead.

[...]

A twitch brought away the tangled red hair, and there, sitting up in his bed, was a pale, sad-faced, refined-looking man, black-haired and smooth-skinned, rubbing his eyes and staring about him with sleepy bewilderment.”

(Adventures 143-144)

In this story, it can be concluded that the difference between social and moral punishment is blurry. Holmes' decision to let St Clair go unpunished by the law underscores how justice in the Holmesian canon often operates within a framework that privileges social stability over absolute moral judgment. This ambiguity reinforces the idea that, in Victorian society, maintaining appearances could at times outweigh the imperative to uphold consistent moral standards.

Regarding Victorian morality breach in 'The Adventure of the Speckled Band', the premises are similar. But while 'The Man with the Twisted Lip' reflects the personal

moral failure of an individual who, though guilty, is given a second chance, 'The Adventure of the Speckled Band' presents a clearer example of how moral corruption is intertwined with wealth and power, and how those in positions of authority can break the moral contract with devastating consequences. The criminal in this story is Dr Roylott. It is explained by Helen Stoker that her step-father "[took] a medical degree and went out to Calcutta, where, by his professional skill and his force of character, he established a large practice", along with the fact that Grimesby Roylott is "the last survivor of one of the oldest Saxon families in England" (*Adventures* 174). In this story, it appears clear from the start that Dr Roylott is not only a man of wealth but he also created a reputation for himself for his medical skills. These elements would imply in the Victorian era that he has a moral contract to uphold in society, even more so as a doctor. However, these moral obligations are broken as he murders his step-daughter Julia with the only motive of financial greed. Just like in 'The Man with the Twisted Lip', there is a tension between crime and morality. A member of a higher social class being capable of crime and not following his moral obligations shows that class and crime are more permeable than imagined.

In *The Hound of the Baskervilles*, Arthur Conan Doyle reflects the Victorian era's deep entanglement of morality with the understanding of crime and justice just as well. In the novel, this connection is vividly illustrated in both the characterisations and the story's themes. One of the most prominent examples is the contrast between the Holmes and Watson duo and the criminal mind of Jack Stapleton. Holmes embodies the Victorian ideal of rationalism and self-control. Watson is also an embodiment of many Victorian ideals, in particular through his profession, marriage, humble attitude and proper social etiquette. This is described by Philip Mason in *The English gentleman: the rise and fall of an ideal*, who says that men had "to live up to

what was felt proper for a gentleman, who must live consistently and intelligibly, with self-respect, performing his dues; who must show respect and consideration for women; must be independent and upright, of unblemished reputation.” (20)

Stapleton, on the other hand, is a deceptive figure who hides his identity and manipulates those around him, ultimately violating both legal and moral codes. His criminal behaviour is not simply a legal crime, but also a familial and social one, betraying the moral expectations surrounding family and birth right.

To conclude on this matter, in both ‘The Man with the Twisted Lip’ and ‘The Adventure of the Speckled Band’, the criminals are men of high status who defy the moral codes of their social class. While both stories explore the consequences of moral failings, they also reveal how crime and class are intertwined, and how those ruptures threaten the social order of the time. When it comes to *The Hound of the Baskervilles*, the ambiguous relationship between crime and morality reaches its peak with Stapleton, who violates both legal and familial codes. His manipulation of others puts forward the fragility of social order. Through these stories, Conan Doyle perfectly illustrates the tension between societal norms and the role of justice in restoring order.

D - The Injustice of Women

As we have seen, the tension between morality, crime, and justice in the Sherlock Holmes stories is often shaped by societal structures, particularly those related to class and gender. In many of Doyle's works, the treatment of women in particular reveals the vulnerabilities they faced within the Victorian social order, as they were another part of the population vulnerable to injustice. Women's roles were largely confined to the domestic sphere, their security and social standing tied to their relationships with men, whether fathers, husbands, or other male figures. Daphne Dale, in her 1892 book *Our manners and social customs; a practical guide to deportment, easy manners, and social etiquette* lists many of the duties of the wife, notably that she must strive to please her husband. Dale asserts that "[i]t is her privilege and pleasure to promote domestic felicity and garland her husband's house with the flowers of a sweet and helpful life." (41). This raises significant questions about justice, not only in the legal sense but also on moral and social aspects, where women's agency was often undermined, leaving them at the mercy of a male-dominated society. The three chosen stories reflect these inequities and how they contribute to the broader theme of social order in the canon and through the canon.

In 'The Adventure of the Speckled Band', Helen and Julia's lives reflect the restrictive expectations placed on women in the late-Victorian era, particularly when it comes to marriage and financial autonomy. Helen is dependent on her stepfather's authority, with the promise of financial independence only coming with her upcoming marriage: "[...] in a month or two, I shall be married, with the control of my own income, and

then at least you shall not find me ungrateful.” (*Adventures* 173). Julia, on the other hand, was set to marry but died just before her wedding, reinforcing the idea that a woman’s security in the late-Victorian era was tied to her ability to marry. Both of the sisters, according to their mother’s will, would have been completely safe only once married. This dependency on male guardianship, here through the figure of the stepfather, proves the vulnerability of women in a society that afforded them little agency outside of the traditional housewife role pushed forward. This dependence on male protection underlines the imbalance in societal justice, with women’s freedom and autonomy often subordinated to the decision of men. In the case of Julia’s death, the lack of a clear legal or social system that could protect her from the control of Dr Roylott, points to a gap in the protective justice that should have been afforded to women in the same position as hers.

Similarly, in ‘The Man with the Twisted Lip’, Kate Whitney’s inability to visit Upper Swandam Lane illustrates the strict boundaries of Victorian society. Respectable women were expected to remain in safe and socially approved spaces: “there is an appropriate sphere for women to move in, from which those of the middle class in England seldom deviate very widely. This sphere has duties and occupations of its own, from which no woman can shrink without culpability and disgrace” (Ellis 72-73). Ms. Whitney is a woman of good birth. Watson introduces her as “an old friend and school companion” of his wife, indicating that she and Mary have been friends for a long time (*Adventures* 124). Therefore, it can be deduced that all three of them pertain to the same social class. When Kate Whitney visits Dr Watson, she asks him to look for her husband Isa, implying that she cannot be the one to do so. This is corroborated by Watson, who says: “How could she, a young and timid woman, make her way into such a place, and pluck her husband out from among the ruffians

who surrounded him?” (*Adventures* 124). Kate Whitney’s association with such a low-class area like the East End of London, with opium dens in slums neighbourhoods, would not be proper of her social standing. This distinction between acceptable and unacceptable places highlights how the system at the time worked to uphold social order by enforcing class and gender boundaries. Women who crossed these lines - whether physically, morally or socially - were subject to judgment. This, once again, suggests that their behaviour was directly tied to maintaining the stability of the social order.

In *The Hound of the Baskervilles*, the theme of female vulnerability is less directly explored but can be seen with the character of Beryl Garçia/Beryl Stapleton. Beryl occupies a passive role in the story. She is submissive to the manipulations of her husband who physically abused her. “She shot her arms out from her sleeves, and we saw with horror that they were all mottled with bruises.” (*Adventures* 162). It can be argued that this very well mirrors the societal expectation that women, particularly those in marriage, were often relegated to the role of passive and helpless victims. Once again, their personal agency was controlled by the male figures in their lives. These narratives in Conan Doyle’s work reflect the broader Victorian attitudes towards women, where their safety, social respectability, and financial stability were linked to their relationships with men, leaving them at the mercy of masculine control and male protection. In the larger context of social order, Beryl’s passivity illustrates how women’s lack of agency reflects a mean by which the stability of the social hierarchy was maintained. By keeping women in submissive, passive roles, Victorian society could maintain its sense of order and control. This often came at the expense of the women’s individual rights to self-determination and protection under the law.

The injustice in these stories is not only the crimes themselves, but society's legal and moral institutions which are biased in favour of men. Women, though not inherently guilty, are vulnerable within that system. As such, their fates are often left at the mercy of the male characters around them. The social order in the Victorian context is maintained through rigid gender norms and class divisions. Women's roles are limited, and their interactions with the legal and social spheres are restricted by patriarchal expectations. This shows the connections between law, morality, and gendered power structures in these stories and how it reflects the social dynamics of the time.

PART III -

THE REINFORCEMENT OF SOCIAL ORDER

A - Fact and Fiction: Real Cases, Influence, and Reception

In examining the intersection of law, morality, and justice in Arthur Conan Doyle's Sherlock Holmes stories, it is essential to consider how real-life criminal cases from the late nineteenth-century may have influenced his portrayal of Holmes as a defender of social order. Doyle's works, such as 'The Man with the Twisted Lip', 'The Adventure of the Speckled Band', and *The Hound of the Baskervilles*, may echo sensational crime cases and public anxieties of the time. Detective stories often drew from actual events or were inspired by notorious criminal figures.

In 'The Man with the Twisted Lip', Neville St Clair's character disguises himself as a beggar under the name of Hugh Boone. In the 1840s, Henry Mayhew conducted a thorough study of the poor in London, analysing the life of everyone, from beggars to traders and prostitutes. In the additional fourth volume published in 1861, Andrew Haliday - one of the co-writers of that special volume - mentions that "[i]t is not uncommon to find among these degraded mendicants one who has really been a gentleman, as far as birth and education go" (404). What Haliday is describing in this instance are men who used to be respectable, but eventually met their fall after going bankrupt or playing too much, eventually leading to their social degradation. This societal anxiety about hidden poverty and the loss of status resonates with the

story's central premise. Indeed, while St Clair's position is slightly different as he does return to his gentleman life in the evening, it still aligns with Haliday's claim that these fallen gentlemen beggars considered work beneath them (404). This is corroborated by St Clair's attitude and response when his identity is unveiled.

“Well, you can imagine how hard it was to settle down to arduous work at £2 a week when I knew that I could earn as much in a day by smearing my face with a little paint, laying my cap on the ground, and sitting still.”

(*Adventures* 146).

Thus, it is very likely that Doyle was inspired by beggars in London, drawing inspiration from real-life scenarios. Richard Lancelyn Green, in the notes of the Oxford World's Classic edition of *The Adventures of Sherlock Holmes*, explains additionally that three major sources of inspiration for the story can be clearly identified: 'A Day as a Professional Beggar' published in the magazine *Tit-Bits* in January 1891, a novel by W. M. Thackeray called 'Miss Shum's Husband', and *The Moonstone* by Wilkie Collins. All three of these pieces mention someone disguising as a beggar. Green notes other possible inspiration sources as Dickens' *The Mystery of Edwin Drood*, as evoked priorly, as well as works by French authors Hugo and Zola (*Adventures* 344-346). These intertextual connections reveal the porous boundary between fiction and contemporary realities, enhancing Holmes's role as a mediator between public fears and literary resolution.

When it comes to 'The Speckled Band', it is often said that “[t]he story may be compared with 'The Murders in the Rue Morgue' (1841) by Edgar Allan Poe” (*Adventures* 361). However, according to Green, a very likely inspiration for this short story may have been a story from *Cassell's Saturday Journal* called 'Called on by a Boa Constrictor: A West African Adventure'. The issue from the 14th February 1891

mentions “a dark queer-looking thing hanging down through the ventilator above it [...] I saw to be the head of the largest boa constrictor I had ever seen.” (*Adventures* 361). This echoes the appearance of the snake in ‘The Speckled Band’ which Dr Roylott would put “through the ventilator [...] with the certainty that it would crawl down the rope, and land on the bed.” (*Adventures* 197).

‘The Adventure of the Speckled Band’ also alludes to another important facet of crime - poison. While of course, the story deals with a natural poison, the venom of the snake, poison in general was at the core of many discourses throughout the nineteenth-century. According to Deborah Blum in *The Poisoner’s Handbook*, “A survey of poison prosecutions in Britain found that, by the mid-nineteenth century, arsenic killings were decreasing.” (Blum 13). This evolution in the use of poison may explain why Doyle opted for a more exotic, natural threat: partly distancing his tale from the overtly domestic connotations associated with arsenic murders, while still tapping into Victorian anxieties about invisible or insidious death.

Notably, high-profile cases such as that of Florence Maybrick, convicted in 1889 for allegedly poisoning her husband, kept the subject of toxicology in the public eye. This case, which sparked intense media scrutiny and divided public opinion, likely fed into Doyle’s awareness of poison as a narrative tool that carried strong emotional and moral weight. It is therefore possible that Doyle’s choice to portray a venomous snake was not merely for shock value, but to update the poison motif in line with contemporary fears.

With these examples, it is clear how Doyle toys with the limits between real life and fiction in his work. In recalling life-like elements in his crimes or mysteries, Doyle not only appeals to the reader by piecing the puzzle together but also highlights how the

stories blur the lines between crime in fiction and crime in the real world through the character of Sherlock Holmes. In this way, Doyle's work reinforces the idea that the detective plays a crucial role in preserving social order, offering a solution to the anxieties of Victorian England about crime and miscellaneous news.

B - The Moral Comfort of detection

The popularity of Sherlock Holmes is not only rooted in the intrigue of his investigations but in the reassurance he offers to a public grappling with rapid social and moral transformation. Victorian society experienced exponential change due to industrialisation, urbanisation, and scientific progress. Ketaki Dwivedi, in her paper 'Converging Precincts: Sociology and Sherlock Holmes', introduces her topic by saying indeed that "[i]n the late eighteenth century and early nineteenth century, there was a sense that Western societies were undergoing powerful changes" (67). These changes continued throughout the 19th century, with "changes in technology and opportunities for profit emerging in a rapidly evolving world economy" (O'Brien). After almost a hundred years of important societal changes which came with many doubts, detective fiction offered a space where uncertainty could be safely resolved. The figure of the detective provided a structure in an unstable world. As Ketaki Dwivedi explains, "Victorian crime fictions portrayed detectives as guardians of society" (74). On this topic, Stephen Knight precises that "[a] figure like Holmes, who treated all problems individualistically and who founded his power on the very rational systems which had inhumane implications was a particularly welcome reversal of disturbing currents" (80). Holmes offers moral comfort for "those whose interests lay in the existing social order [and] felt threatened and vulnerable throughout virtually the whole nineteenth century. Naturally they demanded protection." (Clausen 111). He is a figure of stability in a period of increasing anxiety about the disappearance of traditional social structures. This is a point on which

Dwivedi also touches upon in her analysis. She says regarding the existence of Holmes in people's lives that "everything could be explained and controlled in society that was going through a rapid process of modernisation." (74) In this case, Holmes becomes a tool through which the anxieties of British society in the *fin-de-siècle* could be managed. Dwivedi's argument reinforces the idea that Victorian readers turned to fiction in order to regain control. In this role, Holmes embodies not just reason but moral transparency. His adventures consistently "rejected the values and actions that were forbidden and reaffirmed the prevalent values and morality of society" (Dwivedi 74). In doing so, he gave readers the sense that the moral order, even when threatened, could be restored through logic and justice.

This reassurance was all the more powerful in a context where crime was often associated with a distinct and marginalised "criminal class." As J.J. Tobias explains in 'Crime and Industrial Society in the Nineteenth Century', "'crime' was what they did and what they lived by" (11). This makes figures like St Clair and Roylott particularly unsettling: despite their criminal acts, they do not belong to this criminal class. Their apparent respectability blurs the boundary between law-abiding citizens and wrongdoers, creating a sense of threat that feels uncomfortably close to the reader.

As Bonnie Menes notes, "Holmes delves into the problems of class, personal isolation, and property rights created in Victorian England when industrialization and rapid population growth strained old traditions" (38). Holmes's success in exposing hidden truths and restoring order affirmed a collective hope that beneath the chaos, society was still knowable, governable, and fundamentally just.

There are many reasons that could explain the immense popularity of the Sherlock Holmes stories. As Dwivedi explains, there had been a shift in how people perceived and consumed detective fiction before the 1880s and after. According to her “[t]he shift may also be due to the change in the cultural meaning of crime and criminal and a shift from society controlled by spectacle of punishment to be managed by discipline i.e law of the state.” (69)

The creation of the Metropolitan Police in 1829 under Sir Robert Peel - at the time Home Secretary - marked a significant shift in the administration of justice, aiming to professionalise and centralise law enforcement. These reforms led to an increase in arrests, not necessarily because crime itself was rising, but because more officers were present to detect and report offences. “Greater police diligence meant more arrests. More arrests meant more articles in the papers and inflated crime statistics. [...] Thus, both Sindall and Davis maintain that press coverage was the real cause of the ‘crime wave.’” (Casey 379). However, this rise in visible policing had unintended consequences. With more arrests came more coverage in the press, reinforcing the idea that criminality was rampant. Rather than reassuring the public, the growing presence of the police began to generate suspicion. The police, far from being seen as protectors of order, were increasingly perceived as ineffective or even incompetent - especially in the wake of scandals such as those involving Scotland Yard in the 1870s. This climate of institutional distrust created fertile ground for fictional alternatives. It is within this context that a figure like Sherlock Holmes, rational, independent, and infallible, would be received as a necessary symbolic corrective to a justice system that failed to inspire confidence.

Christopher Clausen also notes this society shift, in particular in regards to Doyle's readership and the police: "[T]he prestige of the police was low when Doyle began to write, and this historical fact has something to do with the popularity of an unofficial genius like Holmes." (114). Clausen expands on this and explains that "in the late 1870s, Scotland Yard suffered a scandal" which led to many feeling "inadequately protected" (111). Thus, if the police of the real world are perceived as not competent, at least someone like Holmes will make sure that criminals are found at least when it comes to fiction.

In 'The Man with the Twisted Lip', this is illustrated in the reaction of Officer Bradstreet to St Clair's confession.

"That was it," said Holmes, nodding approvingly;

"I have no doubt of it. But have you never been prosecuted for begging?"

"Many times; but what was a fine to me?"

"It must stop here, however," said Bradstreet.

(*Adventures* 147)

Despite this, as explained by Christopher Pittard, it appears that many middle-class readers were simply craving for "light-reading" (2) as well, which could be another explanation for the detective's popularity. In the last two decades of the nineteenth century, the acclamation of detective novels and stories could be observed easily. In the 1890s, detective fiction "far outweighed any other genre" in *The Strand* (Pittard 2). Pittard associates notably this celebrity with the fact that detective fiction presented its readers with "recognisable and comfortable narrative models through the serial format" (5). This is corroborated by Stephen Knight in *Form and Ideology in*

Crime Fiction, who says that “the reader of *The Strand* would not have found this month’s story quite like the previous one”, which would of course make it appealing for there were always new stories to be solved. (76). This would have, once again, reinforced the reassurance created by the short stories. Pittard also suggests that the fact that Holmes always caught out a criminal with the belief that they will not offend again reassured many on the growing problem that was recidivism in the *fin-de-siècle*, as previously mentioned (8).

The Strand, explains Christopher Pittard, also had a role in Holmes’s mission. He indeed emphasises that “[t]he story emphasises *The Strand*’s purifying mission by equating the act of detection with washing; Holmes states that the key to the mystery is a sponge, which he uses to uncover St Clair’s disguise.” (7). Sherlock Holmes acts as a moral cleanser, linking the act of detection with purification. The metaphor from ‘The Man with the Twisted Lip’ that Pittard points out here reinforces Holmes’s role. It reflects how Victorian readers saw him as a stabilising force who reaffirmed moral stability and cleansing in what they perceived as a crime-filled world.

To quote Stephen Knight to conclude this topic, “major examples of crime fiction not only create an idea (or a hope, or a dream) about controlling crime, but both realise and validate a whole view of the world, one shared by the people who become the central audience to buy, read and find comfort in a particular variety of crime fiction” (2). This shows how the figure of Holmes offered not just narrative resolution, but cultural reassurance to a society struggling with change.

Yet Holmes is not only a reassuring figure for readers. Within the narrative, he plays a more direct role in upholding and restoring the very social order his audience feared was unravelling.

C - Restoring the balance: Holmes as the Guardian of Social Order

Sherlock Holmes does not merely solve crimes; he enacts a larger ideological function by restoring a sense of order in a society increasingly aware of its own instability. In late Victorian England, a time marked by moral anxieties, Holmes' presence becomes a stabilising force, who projects the idea that disorder can be logically taken apart and managed. His detective work is not just about uncovering individual guilt but about containing social contagion. As Dwivedi observes, "Doyle's sleuth thus actively engaged himself to cleanse the late Victorian England of its morally unsavory and dangerous elements and thus removes the threat of contagious degeneration." (73). Holmes' methodical approach to detection is rooted in observation, deduction, and rational inquiry: "Holmes insists that [...] the solution is always immanent in the given facts." (Parker 451). This is what Dwivedi dubs as the "triumph of reason" (69). This triumph reassures readers that the irrational forces that are threatening society can still be subdued through logic and control. This aspect of Holmes' character mirrors a desire to reclaim a predictable and knowable world at a moment when Victorian certainties were slipping away. This desire for rational control connects with the idea that "the social reality as 'fragile and changing' becomes important subject of inquiry for both sociology and detective literature since both constantly test the reality of reality and see more profound hidden ones." (Dwivedi 69). Holmes reveals the hidden forces and intentions beneath the surface of respectable society while reaffirming the boundaries of morality and normalcy.

In many ways, Holmes becomes a symbolic agent of state - an alternate version of what the police could be - even when he operates independently of formal institutions. His interventions offer reassurance that while social reality may sometimes shatter, he remains a figure capable of reassembling its moral coherence. Ketaki Dwivedi asserts in this regard that "Holmes adventures rejected the values and actions that were forbidden and reaffirmed the prevalent values and morality of society." (74). This reaffirmation plays a crucial role in fiction's capacity to regulate social anxiety. The stories do not simply entertain - they restore belief in a world where morality, justice, and social hierarchy continue to make sense. "Victorian crime fictions portrayed detectives as guardians of society," (Dwivedi 74) and Holmes epitomises this archetype by continually intervening in moments of disruption, restoring order, and ensuring that criminality remains contained. This way, it can be considered that Holmes is a conservative detective, as his character strives to maintain many already existing social elements.

Holmes' actions reassert the idea that society, though under threat, can still and should be saved. The detective's intervention suggests that "society is still a great organism [...] that reinstates an idea of status society that is externalized, traditionalist and easily controllable." (Moretti 183). In Doyle's narratives, the law is less about punishment and more about moral clarity. The threat of disruption - whether from foreign criminals, violent male guardians, or class-based breach - is always contained through Holmes' efforts. As Christopher Clausen notes, "[i]n solving them, Holmes does more than simply satisfy his clients or uphold the abstractions of the law. He single-handedly defends an entire social order whose relatively fortunate members feel it to be deeply threatened by forces that only he is capable of overcoming." (112). Here, Holmes operates as a symbolic barrier against

contemporary uncertainty. He offers reassurance that order, justice, and reason still prevail.

In this light, Holmes is not just a character but a guardian of an idealised social order. He functions as both detective and moralist, performing justice in ways that reaffirm the legitimacy of society. By consistently identifying and eliminating threats to stability, he reinforces the fiction of a society that can still be controlled and preserved. Thus, Holmes becomes the keystone in Doyle's literature. He is not merely solving mysteries, but also resolving broader anxieties and stabilising a nation on the cusp of modernity. However one can identify inconsistencies and weaknesses in the character.

D - Blind spots in Holmes's justice

While Sherlock Holmes is often portrayed as the rational agent restoring balance in a chaotic world, this reassuring image conceals significant ambiguities. Holmes operates largely outside the institutional framework of justice, rarely involving courts or formal legal procedures beyond the identification of a culprit. His interventions consistently bypass the judicial system in favour of swift, discretionary solutions. These solutions, although effective on the surface, tend to uphold a specific vision of social order: one that is middle-class, male, and Anglo-centric. The world Holmes restores is not a just world for all, but a world that privileges upper-class values, gender hierarchies, and imperialist norms. As such, those structurally excluded from power, such as women, the working poor, foreigners, and racialised characters, are frequently marginalised in the narrative. They appear less as subjects with agency than as narrative devices: victims, suspects, or obstacles to be resolved.

This selective justice is exemplified in 'The Man with the Twisted Lip', where Holmes uncovers the truth behind the disappearance of Neville St Clair. Although his actions constitute a criminal offence under the 1824 Vagrancy Act as explained previously, Holmes chooses to shield him from prosecution. The reason lies not in legal logic, but in moral and social acceptability: St Clair could not truly be a criminal. He is respectable, educated, and part of the social elite. His crime is forgiven, not because it is minor, but because he does not belong to the class of people expected to commit it. As Audrey Jaffe explains, "St. Clair's indeterminacy — the mobility that allows him to occupy two social places at once — disturbs the possibility of fixing

identity on which that fantasy rests. And that indeterminacy is expressed both in St. Clair's ability to transform himself and in the figures between which he oscillates — the gentleman and the beggar — who were, for the Victorians, ambiguous and often interchangeable entities" (404). His duality reveals the instability of social markers in Victorian England, particularly between the figure of the beggar and that of the gentleman. Both Neville St Clair and Hugh Boone are perceived as ambiguous, as figures living at the expense of others.

The narrative's solution to this disruption is not to confront it, but to erase it. St Clair's face is literally washed by Holmes to reveal his "true" identity. Yet, as Jaffe points out, "Holmes's washing reveals what might well be taken [...] as a description of no one in particular; the passage's fascination lies with what it repeatedly invokes as 'gone' rather than with what remains" (417). The gesture of revelation becomes, paradoxically, an act of erasure. The ambiguity is not resolved but suppressed, and the story regains its sense of coherence by denying the instability it briefly exposed.

This logic extends beyond questions of class. It shapes the gender politics of the stories as well. In 'The Speckled Band', Helen Stoker's vulnerability and implied domestic violence are acknowledged but never fully addressed. As Hennessy and Mohan argue, "The daughter's seduction, along with the race, class, and gender hierarchies it supports, is silenced by the narrative's coherent solution, a coherence which depends on the reader taking up the position of the subject of knowledge offered by Holmes" (399). The narrative marginalises female experience in favour of Holmes's rational mastery. The reader is invited to identify not with the victim, but with the detective.

The illusion of Holmes's justice, then, rests on a deeper act of containment. As Jaffe puts it, "The Man with the Twisted Lip' both constructs and disables detective fiction's fantasy of social control, performing its traditional task of establishing social identity only by disclosing the absence of the identities it seeks to expose" (404). Holmes restores order not by solving problems, but by smoothing over tensions. His justice is efficient precisely because it is selective. It reassures by excluding, and the cost of that reassurance is the silence of those who fall outside the narrative's framework of protection.

CONCLUSION

In the 1890s, an era marked by rapid scientific advancement, urban growth, and shifting social values, Sherlock Holmes emerged not simply as a fictional detective, but as a real life saviour who offered reassurance amidst growing anxiety. His methods, rooted in observation and deduction, offered comfort to a public increasingly uncertain about the capacity of existing institutions to maintain order. As the structures of Victorian Britain strained under the weight of change - whether due to questions about evolution, gender roles, class boundaries, or the effectiveness of the legal system - Holmes stood firm as a symbol of rationality and moral certainty.

Throughout Sir Arthur Conan Doyle's stories, Holmes's interventions consistently act to restore a sense of social equilibrium. His triumphs are not merely about solving crimes, but about re-establishing the boundaries that hold society together. Whether exposing deception, unmasking hidden criminality, or resolving moral ambiguities, Holmes functions as a stabilising force. He often steps in where official law enforcement fails, positioning himself as both an idealised version of justice and a critique of the real-world legal system. The failure of the police in these stories is not incidental. It underscores the need for a higher, almost mythic figure who can cut through inefficiency and corruption with intellectual precision and moral certainty. Importantly, Holmes operates at the intersection of law and morality, two forces often in tension during the late Victorian period. His justice is not always legal in the conventional sense, like in 'The Man with the Twisted Lip' or simply when he is content with the accidental death of the criminal. He chooses which criminals to

expose and which to protect based on a more nuanced moral framework than the law alone allows. In doing so, Doyle's character reflects Victorian values, but also exposes their limitations. Class and gender expectations, for example, deeply influenced who was seen as a criminal and how they were punished.

The popularity of Holmes's character and the detective fiction genre more broadly speaks to a deeper cultural function. Although premising one of the greatest novel categories, these stories were not written in a vacuum. They mirrored the concerns of the day, from fears of social degeneration to anxieties about identity, class mobility, and institutional integrity. In presenting a world where every mystery has a solution and every crime a cause, detective fiction gave readers a sense of moral coherence. Holmes provided emotional and intellectual relief to a middle-class readership who, amidst the breakdown of old certainties, longed for order to be restored - both in fiction and in real life.

Ultimately, Holmes is more than a famous genius detective. He is a cultural mechanism for reaffirming a society's belief in its own order. His ability to expose truth where appearances deceive and to resolve tension where institutions fall short makes him an agent of both narrative closure and ideological reassurance. While the surface of Victorian society might have appeared genteel and structured, the detective story revealed its underlying tensions. Between science and superstition, progress and decline, reason and fear, Holmes stood at the centre of this tumultuous period, reaffirming that truth could be known, justice served, and order maintained. In this way, Holmes offers not a solution to a crisis, but a story in which that crisis can be imagined, managed, and briefly resolved. However, one cannot help but wonder if Holmes plays his role fully, and if he resolves anxiety completely, or just temporarily.

The recurrence of the detective figure in modern popular culture suggests that this narrative function has not disappeared. Today, crime fiction remains one of the most widely consumed genres and contemporary adaptations such as the series *Sherlock* broadcasted from 2010 to 2017 by the BBC, have achieved global popularity. The BBC said that on New Year's Day 2017, over 11 million viewers tuned in to watch the series (*Sherlock - Most Watched Programme*). This enduring success points to a continuing desire for narratives in which chaos is contained, mystery is explained, and justice is ultimately served.

Interestingly, *Sherlock* updates both the detective and his environment to reflect contemporary tensions: cybercrime, terrorism, mental health, state surveillance. While Holmes retains his aura of infallible logic, he now operates within a more ambiguous legal and moral framework, often clashing with modern institutions rather than supplanting them. In doing so, he continues to reassure viewers. While he does not restore a rigid order, he instead navigates the sometimes blurred boundaries of today's justice and truth.

Thus, whether in 1890 or 2025, Holmes serves the same fundamental purpose: he renders disorder intelligible. Even if he cannot permanently resolve society's tensions, he provides a momentary structure through which they can be processed. This may be the secret behind his timeless success.

BIBLIOGRAPHY

Alton, Stephen R. *The Game is Afoot!; The Significance of Donative Transfers in the Sherlock Holmes Canon, Real Property*. *Trust and Estate Law Journal*, Vol. 46, No. 1, Spring 2011, pp. 125-171

Anglo, Mick. *Penny Dreadfuls and Other Victorian Horrors*. London : Jupiter, 1977. *Internet Archive*, <http://archive.org/details/pennydreadfulsot0000angl>. Accessed 11 June 2025

Baym, Nina. "Morality and Moral Tendency." *Novels, Readers, and Reviewers: Responses to Fiction in Antebellum America*, Cornell University Press, 1984, pp. 173-195

BBC - History - British History in Depth: Crime and the Victorians, https://www.bbc.co.uk/history/british/victorians/crime_01.shtml Accessed 4 May 2025

Beddoe, John. *The Races of Britain; a Contribution to the Anthropology of Western Europe*. Bristol, Arrowsmith, 1885. *Internet Archive*, <http://archive.org/details/racesofbritainco00bedd>. Accessed 30 April 2025

Bentley, David. *English Criminal Justice in the 19th Century*. 1st ed., Hambledon Continuum, 1998, p. 36.

Blum, Deborah. *The Poisoner's Handbook, Murder and the Birth of Forensic Medicine in Jazz Age New York*. Penguin Books, 2011

Brendon, Piers. *The Decline and Fall of the British Empire 1781-1997*. Alfred A Knopf, 2008

Cannadine, David. *History in our Time*. Penguin Books, 2001

Cassell's Saturday Journal - The Arthur Conan Doyle Encyclopedia

[https://www.arthur-conan-doyle.com/index.php/Cassell's Saturday Journal](https://www.arthur-conan-doyle.com/index.php/Cassell's_Saturday_Journal)

Accessed 3 Mar. 2025

Casey, Christopher A. 'Common Misperceptions: The Press and Victorian Views of Crime'. *The Journal of Interdisciplinary History*, Vol. 41, No. 3, Winter 2011, pp. 367-391

A Chronology of Social Change and Social Reform in Great Britain in the Nineteenth and Early Twentieth Centuries

<https://victorianweb.org/history/socialism/chronology.html> Accessed 26 Jan. 2025

Clausen, Christopher. 'Sherlock Holmes, Order, and the Late-Victorian Mind'. *The Georgia Review*, Vol. 38, No. 1, Spring 1984, pp. 104-123

Clausson, Nils. 'Degeneration, Fin-de-Siecle Gothic, and the Science of Detection: Arthur Conan Doyle's *The Hound of the Baskervilles* and the Emergence of the Modern Detective Story'. *Journal of Narrative Theory*, Volume 35, No 1, Winter 2005, pp. 60-87

Dale, Daphne. 'Our Manners and Social Customs ; a Practical Guide to Deportment, Easy Manners, and Social Etiquette'. *Women Working, 1800-1930 - CURIOSity Digital Collections*,

<https://curiosity.lib.harvard.edu/women-working-1800-1930/catalog/45-990023418840203941>. Accessed 1 May 2025.

Dickens, Charles. *The Mystery of Edwin Drood, Reprinted Pieces, and Other Stories*. London, Chapman and Hall, 1892. *Internet Archive*,

<http://archive.org/details/mysteryofedwindrdick00rich>. Accessed 18 April 2025

Doyle, Arthur Conan. *The Adventures of Sherlock Holmes*. Oxford World's Classics, 2008

Doyle Arthur Conan Sir. *The Case Book Of Sherlock Holmes*. John Murray, Albemarle Street, London, 1927. *Internet Archive*, <http://archive.org/details/dli.ernet.247971>. Accessed 14 June 2025

Doyle, Arthur Conan. *The Hound of the Baskervilles*. Penguin English Library, 2019

Doyle, Arthur Conan. *Sherlock Holmes : The Major Stories with Contemporary Critical Essays*. Boston : Bedford Books of St. Martin Press, 1994. *Internet Archive*, <http://archive.org/details/sherlockholmesma0000arth>. Accessed 12 June 2025

Doyle, Arthur Conan. *A Study in Scarlet*. Penguin English Library, 2019

Doyle, Arthur Conan. *The War in South Africa: Its Cause and Conduct - The Arthur Conan Doyle Encyclopedia*.

[https://www.arthur-conan-doyle.com/index.php?title=The War in South Africa: Its Cause and Conduct#II. The Cause Of Quarrel](https://www.arthur-conan-doyle.com/index.php?title=The_War_in_South_Africa:_Its_Cause_and_Conduct#II._The_Cause_Of_Quarrel). Accessed 8 May 2025.

Dwivedi, Katak. 'Converging Precincts: Sociology and Sherlock Holmes'. *Sociological Bulletin*, Vol. 67, No. 1, April 2018, pp. 67-83

Ellis, Sarah Stickney and Victorian Women Writers Project. *The Women of England, Their Social Duties, and Domestic Habits*. London, Fisher, son & co, 1839. *Internet Archive*, <http://archive.org/details/womenofenglandth00ellirich>. Accessed 3 May 2025

Emsley, Clive. *Crime and Society in England, 1750-1900*. Harlow, England ; New York : Longman/Pearson, 2005. *Internet Archive*, <http://archive.org/details/crimesocietyinen0000emsl>. Accessed 8 June 2025

'The Establishment of the Metropolitan Police - Enforcing Law and Order – WJEC - GCSE History Revision - WJEC'. *BBC Bitesize*, <https://www.bbc.co.uk/bitesize/guides/z9f4srd/revision/4>. Accessed 8 June 2025.

Foucault, Michel. *Discipline and Punish, The Birth of the Prison*. Second Vintage Books Edition, 1995

Gatrell, V. A. C., and T. B. Hadden. 'Criminal Statistics and Their Interpretation'. *Nineteenth-Century Society*, edited by E. A. Wrigley, Cambridge University Press, 1972, pp. 336–96. *Cambridge University Press*, <https://doi.org/10.1017/CBO9780511896118.009>. Accessed 13 April 2025

Gordon, Meghan R. 'Women: Worldly, Wordy, or Un-written An Analysis of the Women of Sherlock Holmes and the Victorian English Era'. *Rollins Undergraduate Research Journal*, Vol; 5, No. 2, Article 4, Fall 2011

Greenblatt, Stephen, and Catherine Robson. *The Norton Anthology of English Literature, Volume E The Victorian Age*. Tenth edition, W. W. Norton & company, 2018.

Gypsies, Roma or Travellers. <https://victorianweb.org/history/gypsies.html>. Accessed 14 June 2025.

Halsbury, Hardinge Stanley Giffard. *The Laws of England, Being a Complete Statement of the Whole Law of England*. London, Butterworth, 1909. *Internet Archive*, <http://archive.org/details/lawsfenglandbei09hals>. Accessed 30 April 2025

Harrison, Brian. 'Philanthropy and the Victorians'. *Victorian Studies*, Vol. 9, No. 4, June 1966, pp. 353-374

Hay, Douglas. 'Crime and Justice in Eighteenth- and Nineteenth-Century England'. *Crime and Justice*, Vol. 2, 1980, pp. 45-84

Hennessey, Rosemary, and Rajeswari Mohan. "'The Speckled Band': The Construction of Woman in a Popular Text of Empire." *Sherlock Holmes: The Major Stories with Contemporary Critical Essays*, edited by John A. Hodgson, Bedford/St. Martin's, 1994, pp. 389–401.

Ho, Hock Lai. 'Confessions in the Criminal Process'. *The Modern Law Review*, vol. 84, no. 1, 2021, pp. 30–60. *Wiley Online Library*, <https://doi.org/10.1111/1468-2230.12571>. Accessed 9 June 2025

Hodgeson, John A. 'The Recoil of "The Speckled Band": Detective Story and Detective Discourse'. *Poetics Today*, Vol. 13, No. 2, 1992, pp. 309-324

Hoppen, K. Theodore. *The Mid-Victorian Generation, 1846-1886*. Oxford : Clarendon Press ; Oxford ; New York : Oxford University Press, 1998. *Internet Archive*, <http://archive.org/details/midvictoriangene0000hopp>. Accessed 1 May 2025

Horsley, Lee. *Twentieth-Century Crime Fiction*. Oxford University Press, 2005

Jaffe, Audrey. "Detecting the Beggar: Arthur Conan Doyle, Henry Mayhew and 'The Man with the Twisted Lip'." *Sherlock Holmes: The Major Stories with Contemporary Critical Essays*, edited by John A. Hodgson, Bedford/St. Martin's, 1994, pp. 402-427

Jann, Rosemary. *The Adventures of Sherlock Holmes: Detecting Social Order*. New York: Twayne, 1995.

Knight, Stephen. *Form and Ideology in Crime Fiction*. Bloomington : Indiana University Press, 1980. *Internet Archive*, <http://archive.org/details/formideologyincr0000knig>. Accessed 20 April 2025

Kwarteng, Kwasi. *Ghosts of Empire, Britain's Legacies in the Modern World*. Bloomsbury, 2012.

Latest News. | Northern Echo | Friday 21 March 1873 | British Newspaper Archive. <https://www.britishnewspaperarchive.co.uk/viewer/bl/0000087/18730321/005/0003>. Accessed 26 Apr. 2025.

Lyon Cross, Arthur. 'The English Criminal Law and Benefit of Clergy during the Eighteenth and Early Nineteenth Century'. *The American Historical Review*, Vol. 22, No. 3, April 1917, pp. 544-565

Madden, William A. 'Victorian Morality: Ethics Not Mysterious'. *The Review of Politics*, Vol. 23, No. 4, October 1961, pp. 458-471

Madden, William A. 'The Victorian Sensibility'. *Victorian Studies*, Vol. 7, No. 1, Symposium on Victorian Affairs (2), September 1963, pp. 67-97

Makati, Pamela. *A Critical Study of Charles Dickens' Representation of the Socially Disadvantaged*. Master's thesis, University of Fort Hare, 2008

Mason, Philip. *The English Gentleman: The Rise and Fall of an Ideal*. New York: Morrow, 1982. *Internet Archive*, <http://archive.org/details/englishgentleman0000maso>. Accessed 3 May 2025

Mayhew, Henry. *London Labour and the London Poor; a Cyclopædia of the Condition and Earnings of Those That Will Work, Those That Cannot Work, and Those That Will Not Work*. London, Griffin, Bohn, and Company, 1862. *Internet Archive*, <http://archive.org/details/cu31924092592793>. Accessed 3 March 2025

Mayhew, Henry, and William Tuckniss. *London Labour and the London Poor: A Cyclopaedia of the Condition and Earnings of Those That Will Work, Those That Cannot Work, and Those That Will Not Work*. London: Griffin, Bohn, and company, 1861. *Internet Archive*, <http://archive.org/details/londonlabourlond02mayhrich>. Accessed 3 March 2025

McConnell, Sean. *Interpreting the Victorian Courtroom – Journal of Victorian Culture Online*. 27 Feb. 2013, <https://jvc.oup.com/2013/02/27/interpreting-the-victorian-courtroom/>. Accessed 6 June 2025

McDonald, Lynn. 'Theory and Evidence of Rising Crime in the Nineteenth Century'. *The British Journal of Sociology*, Vol. 33, No. 3, September 1982, pp. 404-420

McNabb, John. 'Anthropology by gaslight'. *World Archaeology*, Vol. 49, No. 5, Debates in World Archeology, December 2017, pp. 728-751

Menes, Bonnie. 'Social Science: Sherlock Holmes and Sociology'. *The American Scholar*, Vol. 50, No. 1, Winter 1981, pp. 101-105

Moore, Natasha. 'The Realism of "The Angel in the House": Coventry Patmore's Poem Reconsidered'. *Victorian Literature and Culture*, Vol. 43, No. 1, 2015, pp. 41-61

Moretti, Franco. *Signs Taken for Wonders: Essays in the Sociology of Literary Forms*. London ; New York : Verso, 1997. *Internet Archive*, <http://archive.org/details/signstakenforwon0000more>. Accessed 29 April 2025

O'Brien, Patrick. 'Imperialism and the Rise and Decline of the British Economy, 1688-1989'. *New Left Review*, no. 1/238, Dec. 1999, pp. 48–80.

Parker, Ben. 'The Method Effect'. *Novel: A Forum on Fiction*, Vol. 49, No. 3, The Method Issue, November 2016, pp. 449-466

Pennington, John. "'Eliminate All Other Factors": Fantastic Hesitation in Arthur Conan Doyle's Hound of the Baskervilles'. *Journal of the Fantastic in the Arts*, Vol. 15, No. 2 (58), Spring 2005, pp. 132-143

Perkin, Harold James. *The Origins of Modern English Society 1780-1880*. London : Routledge & K. Paul ; Toronto : University of Toronto Press, 1969. *Internet Archive*, <http://archive.org/details/originsofmoderne00haro>. Accessed 13 June 2025

Pittard, Christopher. '2006 VanArsdel Prize Essay "Cheap, Healthful Literature": "The Strand Magazine". Fictions of Crime, and Purified Reading Communities', *Victorian Periodicals Review*, Vol. 40, No. 1, Spring, 2007, pp. 1-23

Professional Beggars in London. <https://victorianweb.org/authors/reynolds/14.html>. Accessed 14 June 2025.

Rainsford, Dominic. 'Victorian Moral Philosophy and "Our Mutual Friend"'. *Dickens Quarterly*, Vol. 27, No. 4, December 2010, pp. 273-291

Richardson, Shelley. "Marriage." *Family Experiments: Middle-Class, Professional Families in Australia and New Zealand c. 1880–1920*, ANU Press, 2016, pp. 177-216

Semmel, Bernard. *Jamaican Blood and Victorian Conscience; the Governor Eyre Controversy*. Boston, Houghton Mifflin, 1963. *Internet Archive*, <http://archive.org/details/jamaicanbloodvic00semm>. Accessed 30 April 2025

Sherlock - Most Watched Programme across All Channels over Festive Season for Second Year Running.

<https://www.bbc.co.uk/mediacentre/latestnews/2017/bbc.com/mediacentre/latestnews/2017/sherlock-most-watched/>. Accessed 15 June 2025.

"*Sherlock Holmes as Social Critic.*" *The Wilson Quarterly*, vol. 5, No. 1, Winter 1981, pp. 38–39

Sidney Paget Original Sherlock Holmes Drawings & Artwork: Census by Randall Stock. <https://www.bestofsherlock.com/sidney-paget-original-art.htm#holmes>. Accessed 4 May 2025.

Siegel, Jack M., 'The First Citizen of Baker Street'. *Chicago Review*, Vol. 2, No. 2, Spring 1947, pp. 49-55

Smith, Gregory Thomas. *The State and the Culture of Violence in London, 1760-1840*. PhD diss., University of Toronto, Graduate Department of History, 1999

Social Class. <https://victorianweb.org/history/class.html>. Accessed 14 June 2025.

Stashower, Daniel. *Teller of Tales, The life of Arthur Conan Doyle*. Henry and Holt Company, 1999

Stern, Madeline B. 'Sherlock Holmes: Rare-Book Collector: A Study in Book Detection'. *The Papers of the Bibliographical Society of America* , Vol. 47, No. 2, Second Quarter, 1953, pp. 133-155

Stokes, Eric. 'Late Nineteenth-Century Colonial Expansion and the Attack on the Theory of Economic Imperialism: A Case of Mistaken Identity?'. *The Historical Journal*, Vol. 12, No. 2, 1969, pp. 285-301

Tobias, J.J. *Crime and Industrial Society in the 19th Century*. Schocken Books, 1967. *Internet Archive*, <http://archive.org/details/crimeindustrials0000jjto>. Accessed 9 June 2025

Victorian Drug Use.

<https://victorianweb.org/victorian/science/addiction/addiction2.html>. Accessed 14 June 2025.

Wohl, Anthony. *Perceptions of the Poor: Criminality*.

<https://victorianweb.org/history/race/rc9.html>. Accessed 14 June 2025.

Woodward, Jennifer. 'Social Criticism in Arthur Conan Doyle's The Poison Belt: Cataclysm as Contemporary British Tableau'. *Science Fiction Studies*, vol. 45, no. 1, 2018, pp. 129–45.

Worthington, Heather. *Key Concepts in Crime Fiction*. Palgrave Macmillan, 2011

Young, Arlene. 'Virtue Domesticated: Dickens and the Lower Middle Class'. *Victorian Studies*, Vol. 39, No. 4, Summer 1996, pp. 483-511